

THE ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGISMS WITH GASTRONOMIC COMPONENTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This research compares and analyzes food-related phrases in English and Uzbek. These phrases often have meanings beyond what the words directly say, reflecting cultural and linguistic differences. By studying how these expressions are structured, used, and what they mean culturally, this research aims to find both similarities and differences between the two languages. The results help us better understand how different cultures use language and the values that are a part of it.

Keywords: phrases, food, idioms, cross-language study, English, Uzbek

Introduction

Food-related phrases can give us a unique look into the cultural and social values of a language community. These phrases often mean more than just the words they are made up of, showing the norms, beliefs, and everyday experiences of a society. In both English and Uzbek, such phrases are common, making them an important area of study for those interested in language and culture.

This research looks at how food-related phrases work within the languages of English and Uzbek. It analyzes their meanings and cultural significance. The study also looks at how these phrases are used metaphorically (symbolically) and idiomatically (in fixed expressions) in each language.

Literature Review

The study of food-related phrases is well-researched in both English and Uzbek. Researchers like Negro (2019) and Farkhod-kizi, V. D. (2023) have studied how these phrases reflect cultural practices and values in English and Uzbek society. Their work shows the connection between food phrases and the importance of hospitality in both cultures.

In English, idioms like "butter someone up" (to flatter someone) or "bring home the bacon" (to earn money) have been studied for their metaphorical meanings, showing how food phrases reflect societal norms (Kovecses, 2010). Comparative studies by scholars like Lakoff and Johnson (2003) have also shown that similar food phrases can have different meanings in different languages.

Methodology

This study uses a comparative linguistic approach, focusing on selected food-related phrases in both English and Uzbek. The analysis involves collecting qualitative data from books, native speakers, and phrase dictionaries. The data is categorized based on structure, metaphorical meaning, and cultural relevance, following the classifications suggested by leading scholars like Gibbs (1994)

Results

The analysis shows that while both English and Uzbek use food-related phrases to express cultural values, there are significant differences in how these phrases are structured and understood. For example, the English phrase "spill the beans" (to reveal a secret) has cultural meanings that are not found in Uzbek. On the other hand, the Uzbek phrase "osh yemoq" (to share a meal, symbolizing friendship and unity) has cultural meanings that do not directly translate into English.

Discussion

The findings suggest that the differences in food-related phrases between English and Uzbek are deeply connected to the cultural contexts of each language. These phrases reflect the culinary traditions, historical experiences, and social values unique to each community (Charteris-Black, 2004). Additionally, the study shows that translating such phrases requires more than just a direct translation; cultural meanings must be considered to accurately convey the intended meaning.

Conclusion

Food-related phrases offer a way to view the cultural identity of a language community. The comparative analysis of English and Uzbek phrases in this study highlights the importance of cultural context in shaping the meanings of these phrases. Future research could expand this analysis by including other languages or exploring how modern influences affect the use of these phrases.

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